

Collaborating Decision-Making to Enhance Human Relations for a High Level of Administrative Efficiency

Campong B. Daluma

MSU-Lanao National College of Arts and Trades, Marawi City, Philippines

ABSTRACT: The objective of this study was to evaluate how the implementation of a proper decision-making policy will improve human relations on a high level of administrative efficiency in line with existing policies, strategies, and standards which ensure a sustainable process to achieve an efficient and effective role in both performance management and goal achievement in the system. This inquiry used the descriptive method. The designed research instrument consists of twenty (20) highly structured questions in decision-making, which identifies four variables differentiating among types of decision, determining the amount and type of information needed, establishing priorities for action, and anticipating consequences, and twenty (20) predetermined statements on improving human relations that will determine another four variables such as: develop rapport, build trust and confidence, openness and transparency. Purposive sampling was utilized for the school heads. Selected respondents were the thirty-eight (38) school heads from junior high schools and two hundred seventy-eight (278) teachers from Division of Lanao del Norte teaching junior high schools. The study revealed a correlation between decision-making to improve human interactions and a high level of administrative efficiency. This suggests that the two variables reported by school managers and teachers are modestly connected. This demonstrates that the two groups' reactions to decisions aimed at improving human connections have been modestly connected.

KEYWORDS: Administrative efficiency, collaboration, decision-making, enhance human relations.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Schools' Organizations are designed to achieve collective goals that are beyond the capabilities of any individual. In the current landscape, schools must identify its organizational structure that best suits schools' environment and operational needs. A collaborative decision-making is vital in schools especially it involves teachers, students, parents, and community members that affect the school and its students. This method fosters a sense of shared ownership and responsibility among the schools' stakeholders. According to Mendez (2023), effective organizational performance is crucial in contemporary public management and is not just a theoretical concept, but an ongoing agenda for change and improvement. In this context, collaborative management actions are essential for public managers, aiming to achieve organizational goals by encouraging interactions and facilitating multi-organizational partnerships among autonomous public agencies at the territorial level. These collaborative arrangements are expected to address problems that individual organizations cannot solve alone. Collaborative decision-making builds positive relationships and teamwork that school heads aim to in still in colleagues and students. Likewise, collaborative leadership is a crucial source of competitive advantage, but rare are those leaders who were trained to work collaboratively, mainly those at middle and top managerial posts. According to Maalouf (2019), leadership Style also consists of strengthening corporate management style, understanding self-efficacy while improving learning processes. Likewise, Goddard, Goddard, & Tschannen-Moran (2007) asserted that in the educational context, collaboration has emerged as a strategy for improvement. School leaders are increasingly using collaboration among stakeholders as a means to drive successful school change through role expansion. These examples illustrate that having a unified goal in the workplace is driving positive productivity, and fostering collaboration, and it ensures everyone is on the page, working towards organization's objectives.

This study scrutinized and assessed the role of collaboration and sound decision-making policies in enhancing human relations and administrative efficiency. It argues that aligning these efforts with existing policies, strategies, and standards will ensure a sustainable process for achieving effective performance management and goal accomplishment. The key to successful organizational leadership is understanding the organization's core functions, and ensuring that decisions, policies, and strategies are in line with its mission and vision. In this regard, effective decision-making stems from leaders' understanding of success criteria, the scope of available choices, and the risks inherent in each option.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive-survey research design. The purpose of the design is to obtain information concerning the in selecting the school heads. Respondents were the selected thirty-eight (38) school heads from junior high schools and two hundred seventy-eight (278) teachers from Division of Lanao del Norte teaching junior high schools. The purposive sampling was utilized as a non-probability sampling technique where the researcher deliberately selected specific individuals that are most relevant to the objectives of the study. In purposive sampling, the researcher makes choices based on their judgment about who will provide the most valuable data. According to Patton (2002), purposive sampling is used when researchers want to select specific participants who can provide detailed, relevant, and rich information about a phenomenon of interest.

Moreover, attempted to find out the collaborating decision-making to enhance human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency in the Division of Lanao del Norte; an avenue to managerial quality. First, to determine the extent of decision-making for a high level of administrative efficiency manifested by school managers and teachers in terms of: differentiating among types of decision; such are: determining the amount and type of information needed; establishing priorities for action; and anticipating consequences. Second, to assess the extent it enhances human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency manifested by school managers and teachers along with develop rapport; build trust and confidence; openness and transparency; and how positive regard and respect. Third, determine the extent of comparability between the responses of school managers and teachers along with the variables on decision-making and enhance human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency, and finally, to explore the responses of school managers and teachers differ significantly along with the four variables on decision-making for a high level of administrative efficiency.

Additionally, the researcher utilized questionnaire-checklists as primary instruments in generating the necessary information. Some criteria in constructing the self-made measuring instrument were considered. Extra care in designing the data-collection instrument had been employed. First and foremost, the researcher endeavoured to read published materials such as books, journals etc. and unpublished materials such as theses and dissertation that have a bearing to the present study. After making the necessary pilot work, the researcher started to construct accurate and appropriate data collection instrument. In preparing the instrument, a careful look at the variables under study should be considered, the areas, the consistency, and accuracy of the content of the predetermined statements must be carefully envisioned to ensure that all questions will generate the required information and it should be a representative samples of the content of the variable being considered.

The designed research instrument consists of twenty (20) structured questions in decision making of which identifies four variables – differentiating among types of decision, determining the amount and type of information needed, establishing priorities for action and anticipating consequences and another twenty (20) predetermined statements on enhance human relations which determines another four variables – develop rapport, build trust and confidence, openness and transparency and show positive regard and respect. The data collected was treated using the statistical tools such are: weighted mean, six-point continuum, rank, t-test and z-test with the help of professional statistician to analyze and interpret data collected.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents all the data gathered upon retrieving all the instruments used. Proper analysis of data and interpretation was applied. The various data are presented in this table in the order that they were posted in the problem statement.

On the extent of decision-making for a high level of administrative efficiency manifested by school managers and teachers in terms of differentiating among the types of decision, table 1.1 gives the data on differentiating among types of decision on decision-making for a high level of administrative efficiency. There are presented in rank order based on 6-point scale. The entirety showed that the school leaders have —always manifestedl differentiating among types of Decision on Decision-making. This was exposed by an overall average weighted mean of 5.31 as extracted from the average mean of 5.62 from the school heads and 5.00 from the teachers with its corresponding response category of —always manifestedl and —almost always manifestedl. This was evident by keeping records for implemented decisions religiously crafted by the superior with average weighted mean 5.70; allowed teachers to implement routine decisions with 5.58; improvised decisions coming from superiors to suit the conditions and needs of their level with 5.47; consulted with subordinates in crafting a decision with 5.26; and employed alternatives in implementing decisions to suit the level and conditions of the school having 4.55.

Table 1.1. Differentiating Among Types on Decision - Making for a High Level of Administrative Efficiency

Indicators	School Heads N=38			Teachers N= 278			AWM	RC	R
	TWP	TW	AD	TWP	WM	AD			
	1. Consulted with subordinates in crafting a decision	220	5.79	AM	1315	4.73			
2. Implemented religiously decisions crafted by the school head/supervisor.	218	5.74	AM	1586	5.67	AM	5.70	AM	1
3. Modified decisions coming from the superiors to suit the conditions and need of their level.	200	5.26	AM	1579	5.68	AM	5.47	AM	3
4. Employed alternatives in implementing decisions to suit the level and conditions of the school.	220	5.79	AM	921	3.31	SM	4.55	AAM	5
5. Allowed teachers to implement routine decisions.	210	5.53	AM	1565	5.63	AM	5.58	AM	2
Average Mean	214	5.62	AM	1391	5.00	AAM	5.31	AM	

Legend: 6 - (5.17-6.00)-Always Manifested(AM), 5 - (4.34- 5.16)-Almost Always Manifested (AAM), 4 - (3.51-4.33) -Often Manifested (OM), 3- (2.683.50)-Sometimes Manifested (SM), 2 - (1.84- 2.67)-Rarely Manifested (RM), 1 - (1.00-1.83)-Never Manifested (NM)

On determining the amount and type of information needed on Decision-making for a High Level of Administrative Efficiency, the results shown that the school heads and teachers —often manifestedl of determining the amount and type of information needed on decision-making for a high level of administrative efficiency as can be shown from table 1.2. This was justified by an overall average weighted mean of 4.13 with —often manifestedl response category as specifically exposed from the average mean of 5.17 from the school heads and 3.08 from the teachers with its corresponding response category of —always manifestedl and —sometimes manifestedl. This was particularly exhibited by exploring options before formulating decisions with average weighted mean 4.76; ensured the decisions made is acceptable to subordinates with 3.76; gathered sufficient information from stakeholders before formulating decisions with 3.79; justified actions based from decision made by extracting appropriate information with 4.25; and redirected judgment decisions to rectify errors having 4.08.

Table 1.2. Determining the amount and type of information needed on Decision – Making for a High Level of Administrative Efficiency

Indicators	School Heads N=38			Teachers N= 278			AWM	RC	R
	TWP	TW	AD	TWP	WM	AD			
	1. Explored options before formulating decisions.	209	5.50	AM	1120	4.03			
2. Ensured that decisions made is acceptable to subordinates.	189	4.97	OM	1009	3.63	OM	3.76	OM	5
3. Gathered sufficient information from stakeholders before formulating decisions.	220	5.79	AM	755	2.72	SM	4.25	OM	2
4. Justified actions base from decision made by extracting appropriate information.	220	5.79	AM	755	2.72	SM	4.25	OM	2
5. Redirected judgement decisions to rectify error.	217	5.71	AM	680	2.45	RM	4.08	OM	3
Average Mean	197	5.17	AM	857	3.08	SM	4.13	OM	

Legend: 6 - (5.17-6.00)-Always Manifested(AM), 5 - (4.34- 5.16)-Almost Always Manifested (AAM), 4 - (3.51-4.33) -Often Manifested (OM), 3- (2.683.50)-Sometimes Manifested (SM), 2 - (1.84- 2.67)-Rarely Manifested (RM), 1 - (1.00-1.83)-Never Manifested (NM)

It is found out that school heads and teachers are —almost always manifestedl of anticipating consequences on decision-making with an overall average weighted mean value of 4.86 as can be seen from table 1.3. The average weighted mean of school heads’

responses is 5.72 which falls on —always manifested and for teachers is 3.99 means —often manifested. Evidently, it was emphasized by estimating the nature and number of individuals or referent groups to which decision is relevant; considering the intensity of the identification of each individual or group; presuming rationality of the decision to each individual or group; accommodating the perceptions and value orientations of subordinates in decision making; and preparing on the impact of decision made from the teachers and learners with an average weighted mean values 4.87, 4.40, 4.95, 5.27, and 4.79 respectively.

Table 1.3. Establishing Priorities for Action on Decision Making a High Level of Administrative Efficiency

Indicators	School Heads N=38			Teachers N= 278			AWM	RC	R
	TWP	TW	AD	TWP	WM	AD			
1. Estimated the nature and number of individuals or referent groups to which decisions is relevant.	222	5.84	AM	1086	3.91	OM	4.87	AAM	3
2. Considered the intensity of the identification of each individual or group.	224	5.89	AM	807	2.90	SM	4.40	AAM	5
3. Presumed rationally of the decision to each individual or group.	198	5.21	AM	1303	4.69	AAM	4.95	AAM	2
4. Accommodated the perceptions and value orientation of subordinates in decision making.	224	5.89	AM	1290	4.64	AAM	5.27	AM	1
5. Prepared on the impact of decision made from the teachers and learners.	218	5.74	AM	1066	3.83	OM	4.79	AAM	4
Average Mean	217	5.72	AM	1110	3.99	OM	4.86	AAM	

Legend: 6 - (5.17-6.00)-Always Manifested(AM), 5 - (4.34- 5.16)-Almost Always Manifested (AAM), 4 - (3.51-4.33) -Often Manifested (OM), 3- (2.683.50)-Sometimes Manifested (SM), 2 - (1.84- 2.67)-Rarely Manifested (RM), 1 - (1.00-1.83)-Never Manifested (NM)

Table 2.1. Develop Rapport to Enhance Human Relations for a High Level of Administrative Efficiency

Indicators	School Heads N=38			Teachers N= 278			AWM	RC	R
	TWP	TW	AD	TWP	WM	AD			
1. Elicited desire to focus on subordinates’ concern, aspirations and ideals.	220	5.79	AM	1072	3.86	OM	4.82	AAM	4
2. Established line of communication by both verbal and non-verbal means.	200	5.26	AM	1315	4.73	AAM	5.00	AAM	3
3. Endeavored to foster and enhance professional relationship by means of communication.	208	5.47	AM	1524	5.48	AM	4.48	AM	1
4. Recognized subordinate’s worth and distinctiveness.	219	5.76	AM	979	3.52	OM	4.64	AAM	5
5. Exhibited interest in working with any of the subordinate’s as a team without reservation.	200	5.26	AM	1576	5.67	AM	5.47	AAM	2
Average Mean	209	5.51	AM	1293	4.65	AAM	5.08	AAM	

Legend: 6 - (5.17-6.00)-Always Manifested(AM), 5 - (4.34- 5.16)-Almost Always Manifested (AAM), 4 - (3.51-4.33) -Often Manifested (OM), 3- (2.683.50)-Sometimes Manifested (SM), 2 - (1.84- 2.67)-Rarely Manifested (RM), 1 - (1.00-1.83)-Never Manifested (NM)

On the problem number two, the extent it enhances human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency manifested by school managers and teachers, table 2.1 showed that It is generally reflected on the table that the two groups are –almost always manifestedl of developing rapport to enhance human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency with an overall average weighted mean value of 5.08. The average weighted mean of school heads’ responses is 5.51 which falls on –always manifested

and for teachers is 4.65 means –almost always manifestedl. It was evidently shown by eliciting desire to focus on subordinate’s concern, aspirations and ideals; establishing the line of communication by both verbal and non-verbal means; endeavoured to foster and enhance professional relationship by means of communication; recognizing subordinate’s worth and distinctiveness; and Exhibited interest in working with any of the subordinate’s as a team without reservation with an average weighted mean values 4.82, 5.00, 5.48, 4.64, and 5.47 respectively.

Moreover, table 2.2, Build Trust and Confidence to Enhance Human Relations for a High Level of Administrative Efficiency, results revealed as manifested by the two groups with an overall average weighted mean 4.72. It is presented that school heads’ responses computed average weighted mean 5.65 is categorized as—always manifestedl while teachers’ responses average weighted mean is 3.79 means —often manifestedl. Specifically, the following items are elaborated with their corresponding average weighted mean values: Endeavoured to gain teachers trust by being consistent and honest (4.86); Showed credibility and reliability to invoke colleague’s trust (4.83); possessed confidence that the teacher can complied a delegated task (4.77); Exhibited the belief that the teachers possess the ability to perform the authority delegated (4.64); and endeavoured to protect the interest of teachers (4.52).

Table 2.2. Build Trust and Confidence to Enhance Human Relations for a High Level of Administrative Efficiency

Indicators	School Heads N=38			Teachers N= 278			AWM	RC	R
	TWP	TW	AD	TWP	WM	AD			
	1. Showed credibility and reliability to invoke colleague’s trust.	222	5.84	AM	1062	3.82			
2. Endeavoured to gain teachers trust by being consistent and honest.	222	5.84	AM	1077	3.87	OM	4.86	AAM	1
3. Possessed confidence that the teacher can complied a delegated task.	210	5.53	AM	1114	4.01	OM	4.77	AAM	3
4. Endeavoured to protect the interest of teachers.	202	5.32	AM	1033	3.72	OM	4.64	AAM	5
5. Exhibited the belief that the teachers possess the ability to perform the authority delegated.									2
Average Mean	215	5.65	AM	1054	3.79	OM	4.72	AAM	

Legend: 6 - (5.17-6.00)-Always Manifested(AM), 5 - (4.34- 5.16)-Almost Always Manifested (AAM), 4 - (3.51-4.33) -Often Manifested (OM), 3- (2.683.50)-Sometimes Manifested (SM), 2 - (1.84- 2.67)-Rarely Manifested (RM), 1 - (1.00-1.83)-Never Manifested (NM)

Commonly, the school managers and teachers’ responses on openness and transparency to enhance human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency are interpreted as –almost always manifestedl with overall average weighted mean 4.81 as shown from table 3. The findings revealed that the responses of the school heads are within the range –always manifestedl with average weighted mean 5.49 while for teachers’ responses generated average weighted mean is 4.13 which means —often manifestedl. It is clearly visible to the following items with their corresponding average weighted mean values: Showed oneself as a model by being truthful and straight forward (5.68); Exhibited appreciation of the compliance of teacher to the authority delegate (5.38); Endeavoured to eliminate any inhibition that will generate suspicion and doubt (4.92); Established clear cut practice conducive to develop subordinate’s ability to exercise delegated authority (4.68); and rotated the authority delegation to the subordinates while out in school for official business (3.38).

Additionally, Table 2.4 illustrates the responses of the school heads and teachers on showing positive regard and respect to enhance human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency. The table showed an overall average weighted mean of 5.64 which means —always manifestedl. It is emphasized that both responses of the two groups are interpreted as —always manifestedl with an average weighted mean values of 5.78 and 5.49 respectively. In such a way the following items supported with their corresponding average weighted mean values: Recognized teachers value, dignity and rights (5.83); Displayed interest in working with any of the subordinates as a team without reservation (5.82); Exhibited active listening every time there is a dialogue (5.74); Conducted regular

dialogue among the subordinates (5.50); and encouraged teachers to ventilate their feelings and ideas about their classroom work experiences (5.30).

Table 2.3. Openness and Transparency of Enhance Human Relations for a High Level of Administrative Efficiency

Indicators	School Heads N=38			Teachers N= 278			AWM	RC	R
	TWP	TW	AD	TWP	WM	AD			
	1. Showed oneself as a model by being truthful and straight forward.	219	5.76	AM	1554	5.59			
2. Endeavoured to eliminate any inhibition that will generate suspicion and doubt.	220	5.79	AM	1127	4.05	OM	4.92	AAM	3
3. Exhibited appreciation of the compliance of teacher to the authority delegate.	220	5.79	AM	1384	4.98	AAM	5.38	AM	2
4. Established clear cut practice conducive to develop subordinates ability exercise delegated authority.	213	5.61	AM	1044	3.76	OM	4.68	AAM	4
5. Rotated the authority delegation to the subordinates while out in school for official business.	171	4.50	AAM	628	2.26	RM	3.38	SM	5
Average Mean	209	5.49	AM	1147	4.13	OM	4.81	AAM	

Legend: 6 - (5.17-6.00)-Always Manifested(AM), 5 - (4.34- 5.16)-Almost Always Manifested (AAM), 4 - (3.51-4.33) -Often Manifested (OM), 3- (2.683.50)-Sometimes Manifested (SM), 2 - (1.84- 2.67)-Rarely Manifested (RM), 1 - (1.00-1.83)- Never Manifested (NM)

Table 2.4. Show Positive Regard and Respect to Enhance Human Relations for a High Level of Administrative

Indicators	School Heads N=38			Teachers N= 278			AWM	RC	R
	TWP	TW	AD	TWP	WM	AD			
	1. Recognized teachers' value, dignity and rights.	227	5.97	AM	1582	5.69			
2. Conducted regular dialogue among the subordinates.	202	5.32	AM	1579	5.68	AM	5.50	AM	4
3. Exhibited active listening every time there is a dialogue.	224	5.89	AM	1550	5.58	AM	5.74	AM	3
4. Encouraged teaching to ventilate their feelings and ideas about their classroom work experiences.	220	5.79	AM	1337	4.81	AAM	5.30	AM	5
5. Displayed interest in working with any of the subordinates as a team without reservation.	226	5.95	AM	1582	5.69	AM	5.82	AM	2
Average Mean	220	5.78	AM	1526	5.49	AM	5.64	AM	

Legend: 6 - (5.17-6.00)-Always Manifested(AM), 5 - (4.34- 5.16)-Almost Always Manifested (AAM), 4 - (3.51-4.33) -Often Manifested (OM), 3- (2.683.50)-Sometimes Manifested (SM), 2 - (1.84- 2.67)-Rarely Manifested (RM), 1 - (1.00-1.83)- Never Manifested (NM)

Additionally, on problem number three, the extent of comparability between the responses of school heads and teachers along with the variables on decision-making and enhance human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency. Table 3 reveals the comparability between the responses of the school managers and teachers along with the variables on decision-making and enhance human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency. As presented, the responses of the school administrators between decision-making and human relations have no difference because their adjectival equivalent is the same which fall on –always manifestedl with generated average weighted mean values of 5.49 and 5.61 respectively.

Table 3. Extent of Comparability Between the Responses of School Heads and Teachers Along with the Variables on Decision-Making and Enhance Human Relations for a High Level of Administrative Efficiency

Indicators	School Heads N=38			Teachers N= 278			AWM	RC	R
	TWP	TW	AD	TWP	WM	AD			
	Decision Making								
1. Differentiation among types of decision.	213.6	5.62	AM	1391	5.0	AAM	5.31	AM	1
2. Determining the amount and type of information needed.	196.6	5.62	AM	857	3.08	SM	4.13	OM	4
3. Establishing priorities for action.	209.6	5.52	AM	790	2.84	SM	4.18	OM	3
4. Anticipating consequences.	214.8	5.65	AM	1110	3.99	OM	4.82	AAM	2
5. Displayed interest in working with any of the subordinates as a team without reservation.									
Average Mean	209	5.49	AM	1037	3.73	OM	4.61	AAM	
Enhance Human Relations									
1. Develop Rapport	209.4	5.51	AM	1293	4.65	AAM	5.08	AAM	2
2. Build trust and confidence.	214.8	5.65	AM	1054	3.79	OM	4.72	AAM	4
3. Openness and Transparency.	208.6	5.49	AM	1147	4.13	OM	4.81	AAM	3
4. Show positive regard and respect.	219.8	5.78	AM	1526	5.49	AM	5.64	AM	1
Average Mean	213	5.61	AM	1255	4.52	AAM	5.06	AAM	

Legend: 6 - (5.17-6.00)-Always Manifested(AM), 5 - (4.34- 5.16)-Almost Always Manifested (AAM), 4 - (3.51-4.33) - Often Manifested (OM), 3- (2.683.50)-Sometimes Manifested (SM), 2 - (1.84- 2.67)-Rarely Manifested (RM), 1 - (1.00-1.83)- Never Manifested (NM)

However, the teachers’ responses between the two variables are slightly different because their responses for decision –making generates an average weighted mean of 3.73 which is categorized as —often manifestedl while their human relations responses provide an average weighted mean of 4.52 which means —almost always manifested". Eventually, there is no difference between the responses of the two groups of the first and second set of variables since they are within the range of —almost always manifestedl that generates an average weighted mean values of 4.61 and 5.06 respectively. This implies that the two groups almost always demonstrate on decision-making and human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency. This means that the two parties almost always show a high degree of functional performance in decision-making and human relations.

Moreover, it was found out in table 4 the significant difference of the responses of the school managers and teachers along with the four variables on decision-making and human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency. As revealed, there is a significant difference between the four variables because the t-test computed value 3.501 is greater than the t-test tabular value 2.447 with 6 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance. Their corresponding standard deviation values of the responses of the school managers are 0.2205 while the teachers are 0.9824. Thus, Ho is rejected.

Table 4. Significant Difference Between the Responses of School Heads and Teachers in Decision-Making Along with the Four Variables on Decision-Making for a High Level of Administrative Efficiency

VARIABLES	SCHOOL HEADS		TEACHERS	
	X1		X2	
	WM	RC	WM	RC
Differentiating among types of Decision	5.62	AM	5.00	AAM
Determining the amount and type of information needed	5.17	AM	3.08	SM
Establishing priorities for Action	5.52	AM	2.84	SM
Anticipating consequences	5.65	AM	3.99	OM
Average Mean	5.49	AM	3.73	OM
Standard Deviation	0.2205		0.9824	

Table 5 reveals the significant difference of the responses of school heads and teachers along with the four variables on human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency. As shown, the responses of the two groups along with the four variables of human relations differ significantly since the computed t-test value 2.905 is greater than the tabular value 2.447 with 6 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. The school managers' responses have 0.1352 standard deviation value while teachers' responses have 0.7400.

Table 5. Significant Difference Between the Responses of School Heads and Teachers in Decision-Making Along with the Four Variables that Enhance Human Relations for a High Level of Administrative Efficiency

VARIABLES	SCHOOL HEADS		TEACHERS	
	X1		X2	
	WM	RC	WM	RC
Develop Rapport	5.51	AM	4.65	AAM
Build Trust and Confidence	5.65	AM	3.79	OM
Openness and transparency	5.49	AM	4.13	OM
Show positive regard and respect	5.78	AM	5.49	AM
Average Mean	5.61	AM	4.52	AAM
Standard Deviation	0.1352		0.7400	

Table 5 indicates that the response of the two groups along with the four variables, vary in relation to human relations. It can be noted that the four variables have been expressed somewhat inconsistently. This is an indication that the responses of the two groups along with the four variables vary in relation to human relations. It was observed that the four variables have been expressed somewhat inconsistently.

Finally, table 6 presents the correlation exist between the responses of school heads and teachers on decision- making to enhance human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency as responded by the school heads and teachers. The results revealed that correlation exist between decision-making to enhance human relations for a high level of administration efficiency. This

indicates that the two variables responded by the school managers and teachers are moderately correlated because the Pearson r value 0.6992 is within the range of interpretation ± 0.41 to ± 0.70 which means have moderate correlation at 5% level of significance.

Table 6. Correlation Between Decision-Making to Enhance Human Relations for a High Level of Administrative Efficiency

VARIABLES	Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r)	α
Decision-making to Enhance Human Relations for a High Level of Administrative Efficiency	0.6992	5 %

Interpretations:

± 0.00 to ± 0.20 = slight correlation, almost negligible relationship.

± 0.21 to ± 0.40 = slight correlation, definite but small relationship.

± 0.41 to ± 0.70 = moderate correlation, Substantial relationship

± 0.71 to ± 0.90 = high correlation, marked relationship

± 0.91 to ± 1.00 = very high correlation, very dependable relationship

Table 6 implied that decision-making to enhance human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency is having substantial relationships. This further indicates that responses of the two groups on decision making to enhance human relations were moderately associated.

4. CONCLUSION

This study found out that the school heads have always manifested on differentiating among types of decision on Collaborative Decision-making. The school heads and teachers were often manifested of determining the amount and type of information needed on decision-making for a high level of administrative efficiency. It is found out that school managers and teachers were almost always manifested of anticipating consequences on decision-making for a high level of administrative efficiency. With regard to enhance human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency, develop rapport as the first variable was almost always manifested by the two groups. On building trust and confidence for a high level of administrative efficiency was responded by the two groups with almost always manifested. For openness and transparency to enhance human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency, it is responded almost always manifested by the two groups through showing oneself as a model. Finally, on showing positive regard and respect to enhance human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency, the responses of the school managers and teachers were always manifested.

With regard to comparability of between the responses of the school heads and teachers along with the variables on decision-making and enhance human relations for a high level of administrative efficiency, it is revealed that there is no difference between the responses of the two groups of the first and second set of variables since they are within the range of —almost always manifested. As to the results of significant difference, it is revealed, there is a significant difference between the four variables. Similarly, as shown, the responses of the two groups along with the four variables of human relations differ significantly.

Generally, it is revealed in this study that correlation exist between decision-making among the schools’ stakeholders to enhance human relations for a high level of administration efficiency. This indicates that the two variables responded by the school heads and teachers are moderately correlated.

REFERENCES

1. Bryk, A.S. (2020). Improvement in Action: Advancing Quality in America’s Schools. Stanford, CA: Carnegie Foundation for the Advancement of Teaching.
2. Bryk, A. S., & Schneider, B. (20). Tru20st in schools: A core resource for school reform. Educational leadership, 60(6), 40–45. <https://www.ascd.org/el/articles/trust-inschools-a-core-resource-for-school-reform>

3. Elmore R., (2008). Leadership as the practice of improvement. Improving School Leadership, Volume 2: Case Studies on System Leadership – ISBN: 978-92-64-03308-5
4. Fullan, M. (2019). Nuance: Why some leaders succeed and others fail. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin.
5. Goddard, Goddard, & Tschannen-Moran, (2007). Instructional Leadership: A Pathway to Teacher Collaboration and Student Achievement
6. Hargreaves, A (2020). 'Large-scale assessments and their effects: The case of mid-stakes tests in Ontario', Journal of Education Change, 21, p 393–420.
7. Harris, A. (2021). System leaders and system leadership: exploring the contemporary evidence base. School Leadership Management
8. Leithwood, K., (2020). A Review of Evidence about Equitable School Leadership. Educ. Sci. 2021, 11, 377
9. Maalouf, G. (2019). Effects of collaborative leadership on organizational performance. International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development. 6(1):138-144. DOI: 10.22271/ijmrd. 2019.v6. i1.25
10. Mendez, N., (2023). Do Collaborative Management Actions Lead to Better Organizational Outcomes? <https://doi.org/10.1080/01900692.2023.2256994>
11. Patton, M. Q. (2002). Qualitative research and evaluation methods (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA

Cite this Article: Daluma, C.B.(2025). Collaborating Decision-Making to Enhance Human Relations for a High Level of Administrative Efficiency. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(7), pp. 3766-3775. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i7-66>